

1 **Soil heterotrophic CO₂ emissions from tropical high-elevation ecosystems**
2 **(Páramos) and their sensitivity to temperature and moisture fluctuations**

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23 **Keywords:** Páramos, heterotrophic respiration (R_H), heterotrophic communities,
24 climate change, soil C-rich soils

25

26 **Summary**

27 Increasing temperatures and changes in the intensity and frequency of precipitations may
28 impact the ability of tropical high-elevation Andean ecosystems (Páramos) to store and
29 retain carbon (C). We, therefore, examined how warming and fluctuations in soil moisture
30 could influence soil CO₂ emissions from heterotrophic respiration (R_H, the result of
31 microbial respiration), of two Páramos of contrasting climatic regimes within their area
32 of distribution. We here show high sensitivity of both R_H and Q₁₀ under warmer and
33 fluctuating moisture conditions. Together with the high rates of C-normalized R_H
34 compared to other soil C-rich ecosystems from higher latitudes (2 μmol gC⁻¹ h⁻¹ versus
35 0,4 μmol gC⁻¹ h⁻¹, respectively) our results evidenced how soil heterotrophic-derived CO₂
36 emissions could potentially increase under expected climate scenarios, eventually altering
37 the capacity of soil Páramos to sequester C.

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41 Páramos are ecosystems distributed in the Andean regions at altitudes that range between
42 2800 and 4700 m a.s.l. (Figure S1). They cover approximately a total of 35,000 km²
43 between latitudes 11°N and 8°S (Madrñan et al., 2013). Low temperatures, especially
44 during night time (minimum monthly values ranging between -4 and 6 °C) and conditions
45 of soil pore water saturation have led to slow decomposition rates and a large buildup of
46 organic matter through centuries (Podwojewski *et al.*, 2002; Poulénard *et al.*, 2003). This
47 makes Páramos some of the most important carbon (C) sinks in the tropics storing six-
48 fold more C per area than tropical forests (Hofstede, 1999). However, projections made
49 for the northern Andean region converge on a mean increase in mean annual temperature
50 (MAT) of $3 \pm 1.5^\circ\text{C}$ during the next century (Buytaert *et al.*, 2011) and changes in the
51 intensity and frequency of precipitations (IPCC 2014) that might impact their ability to
52 store and retain C. In this regard, understanding the potential sensitivity to weather
53 fluctuations of soil heterotrophic respiration (R_H), the result of the aerobic decomposition
54 of soil organic matter (SOM), and a major contributor of terrestrial soil CO₂ emissions
55 (Bond-Lamberty et al. 2004), would be key to interpret how vulnerable Páramos SOC
56 stocks could be in future scenarios.

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58 To address the uncertainty, we designed a factorial experiment to evaluate the sensitivity
59 of soil R_H from Páramo ecosystems to fluctuations in weather conditions, taking into
60 account warming (from ambient-current temperatures to temperatures resembling "heat-
61 wave" scenarios) and soil moisture fluctuations (from conditions of total water saturation
62 to extreme drought).

63

64 To study potential differences in the responses associated with historical climatic
65 conditions, soil samples were collected from two Páramo complexes with similar

66 elevation but different precipitation and temperature regimes: the Páramo of Verjón
67 (“Parque Ecológico Matarredonda”, hereinafter MT) (4°33’38.1” N and 74°0’7.3” W) is
68 colder (mean annual temperature of 8.7°C) but drier (mean precipitation of 1178 mm)
69 than the Chingaza Páramo complex (“Chaleche”, hereinafter CH) (4°58’18.1”N and
70 74°47’5.8”W), which has a mean annual temperature of 10.1°C and a mean annual
71 precipitation of 1316 mm (<http://www.worldclim.org/>). No differences in soil total carbon
72 (C), nitrogen (N), and sulphur content (S) were found between the two sites (Table 1, S1,
73 S2). A total of 10 composite soil samples (3 subsamples to a total of 1 kg each) were
74 collected with a shovel from each of the two Páramo complexes following a line transect
75 methodology (each 20 m during approx. 200 m transect). Samples were collected from
76 the first 30 cm of top soil underneath individual plants belonging to the genus *Espeletia*
77 (e.g. *Espeletia grandiflora*, *Espeletia killipii*) (Morales *et al.*, 2007), one of the most
78 emblematic and representative genus of the Páramo flora (de los Ángeles *et al.*, 2002).
79 After hand-mixing and manual removal of large roots and wood debris, subsamples (20
80 to 40 g) of each soil composite sample were incubated at one of four treatments: 9, 22,
81 29, or 37 °C. Incubation temperature was maintained stable by controlling the thermostat
82 either of a refrigerator (9 °C) or of an incubator (22, 29, or 37 °C) (Figure S2).
83 Heterotrophic respiration (R_H), soil temperature and soil moisture (SWC) were measured
84 daily in all 80 soil subsamples during 3-4 weeks following the protocol of Curiel Yuste
85 *et al.* (2007, 2011). Soil moisture was evaluated by monitoring sample weight losses
86 throughout a natural soil drying process, starting from total water saturation of the soil
87 pore space (SWC = 100%), which is the natural condition generally experienced by these
88 sites (e.g. low soil O₂ diffusivity). Heterotrophic respiration (R_H) was measured with an
89 Infrared Gas Analyzer (IRGA; PP-Systems) and soil-surface temperature with and
90 infrared thermometer (Mastercool, 52224-A-SP). The temperature sensitivity of R_H was

91 assessed by applying a Q_{10} exponential function to rates of R_H from soils incubated at
92 different temperatures following Curiel Yuste et al. (2007) and (2011) (Figures S3). No
93 signs of labile substrate depletion under the warmest conditions (29 and 37°C) was
94 observed after a second rewetting cycle (Figures S4), indicating that the calculated Q_{10} 's
95 were unlikely suspicious of including errors associated with differential labile substrate
96 availability at different temperatures (e.g. Hartley et al., 2007). We further compared
97 obtained values of R_H (normalized by C concentration) with literature values from
98 northern (Boreal, Temperate and Tropical) soil C-rich ecosystems (peatlands/wetlands)
99 and values of soil R_H from incubations similarly performed (e.g. Curiel Yuste et al. 2007).

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101 Rates of R_H were strongly determined by the fluctuating abiotic conditions imposed in
102 the experiment (Figures 1, 2 and 3). On one hand, and in agreement with observations
103 from other C-rich, O_2 -limited ecosystems (Boreal, Temperate and Tropical peatlands, see
104 Figure 4), R_H from soil Páramos were not necessarily limited under total pore water
105 saturation (Figures 1 and 2), when low O_2 diffusivity should limit R_H (e.g. Moyano *et al.*,
106 2012). It is likely that these local microbial communities growing under environmental
107 conditions typically limiting O_2 diffusivity (high altitudes and soil pore water saturation)
108 may have optimized the use of either the deficient O_2 levels and/or of other alternative
109 electron acceptors (e.g. nitrate, Mn (IV), Fe (III), sulfate, CO_2 or SOM) (Conrad 1989;
110 Coates *et al.*, 1998; Vile et al., 2003; Keller & Bridgham, 2007; Corbett et al., 2013).

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112 On the other hand, and as observed for other soil-C rich ecosystems (e.g. Lafleur et al.
113 2005), changes towards warmer and drier conditions further resulted in substantial
114 increases in the temperature sensitivity (Q_{10}) of R_H (Figure 3). The positive effect over
115 soil aerobic metabolism of increasing levels of O_2 diffusivity as soils dried out (e.g.

116 Moyano *et al.*, 2012) and/or the increasing decomposability of more complex organic
117 matter pools under warmer conditions (Bosatta & Ågren 1998; 1999; Conant *et al.*, 2008)
118 could explain this changes in Q_{10} . Inter-site variability in Q_{10} (Figure 3) of soil R_H along
119 the moisture spectra further suggest that responsiveness of R_H to warmer and drier
120 conditions might be strongly dependent on adaptation to local climatic conditions.

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122 Finally, we here show rates of soil R_H (C-normalized) substantially larger than those from
123 other boreal and temperate soil-C rich soils ($2 \mu\text{mol gC}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$ versus $0,4 \mu\text{mol gC}^{-1} \text{h}^{-1}$,
124 respectively) but comparable to rates obtained from other Tropical or Mediterranean
125 ecosystems (Figure 4). Factors such as soil C/N ratio, which generally well correlated
126 with soil organic matter (SOM) decomposition (e.g. Couteaux *et al.* 1995) might explain
127 the observed differences. Indeed, soil C/N ratios obtained from our study (19-18; Table
128 1) were comparably lower than those observed in e.g. permafrost soils (averaging 30 in
129 Treat *et al.*, 2015) or northern peatlands (ranging from 15 to 38; see Bridgham *et al.*,
130 1998).

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132 Concluding, we observed no evidences of R_H limitations under high soil water saturation
133 and increasing Q_{10} 's under warmer and drier scenarios. The observed sensitivity of both
134 R_H and Q_{10} together with the high rates of C-normalized R_H evidenced how soil
135 heterotrophic-derived CO_2 emissions could potentially increase under expected climate
136 scenarios, eventually altering the capacity of soil Paramos to sequester C.

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139 **Acknowledgments**

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141 This work was supported by "becas Santander para jovenes investigadores" and the
142 Spanish Ministry for Economy and Competitiveness (MINECO) with the project
143 VERONICA (CGL2013-42271-P). Funding for this research comes from Eloisa Lasso's
144 FAPA grant P12.160422.001 from Universidad de los Andes and from the Alexander
145 Von Humboldt Institute that funded the soil chemical analysis. The authors want to thank
146 to Prof. Dr. Santiago Madriñán (Laboratorio de Botánica y Sistemática, Universidad de
147 los Andes) for contributing with his expertise and valuable advice on the selection of
148 plots. We want to thank Dr Maria Claudia Lattig Matiz and the Human Genetics group
149 (Universidad de los Andes) for lending us the incubators and the necessary space for the
150 development of this experiment. We also want to thank the Escallón family, owners of
151 the "Rodomonte" farm, located in the town of Sesquile (Chaleche sidewalk) and the
152 "Parque Ecologico Matarredonda" and the Sabogal Family for their selfless help in
153 allowing us to sample their land.

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156 **Bibliography**

- 157 Bond-Lamberty, B., Wang, C. K., Gower, S. T., 2004. A global relationship between the
158 heterotrophic and autotrophic components of soil respiration? *Global Change*
159 *Biology* 10, 1756-1766.
- 160 Bosatta, E., Ågren, G. R. I., 1999. Soil organic matter quality interpreted
161 thermodynamically. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 31, 1889-1891.
- 162 Bridgham, S.D., Updegraff, K., Pastor, J., 1998. Carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus
163 mineralization in northern wetlands. *Ecology* 79, 1545-1561.
- 164 Buytaert, W., Cuesta-Camacho, F., Tobón, C., 2011. Potential impacts of climate change
165 on the environmental services of humid tropical alpine regions. *Global Ecology and*
166 *Biogeography* 20, 19-33.
- 167 Cabaneiro, A., Fernandez, I., Pérez-Ventura, L., Carballas, T., 2008. Soil CO₂ Emissions
168 from Northern Andean Páramo Ecosystems: Effects of Fallow Agriculture.
169 *Environmental Science & Technology* 42, 1408-1415.
- 170 Coates, J. D., Ellis, D. J., Blunt-Harris, E. L., Gaw, C. V., Roden, E. E., Lovley, D. R.,
171 1998. Recovery of Humic-Reducing Bacteria from a Diversity of Environments.
172 *Applied and Environmental Microbiology* 64, 1504-1509.
- 173 Corbett, J.E., Tfaily, M.M., Burdige, D.J., Cooper, W.T., Glaser, P.H., Chanton, J.P.,
174 Partitioning pathways of CO₂ production in peatlands with stable carbon isotopes.
175 *Biogeochemistry* 114, 327-340.
- 176 Conant, R. T., Drijber, R. A., Haddix, M. L., Parton, W. J., Paul, E. A., Plante, A. F., Six,
177 J., Steinweg, J. M., 2008. Sensitivity of organic matter decomposition to warming
178 varies with its quality. *Global Change Biology* 14, 868-877.
- 179 Conrad, R., 1989. Control of methane production in terrestrial ecosystems, p. 39–58. In
180 M. O. Andreae and D. S. Schimel [eds.], *Exchange of trace gases between*
181 *ecosystems and the atmosphere*. John Wiley and Sons.
- 182 Coutteaux, M.-M., Bottner, P., Berg, B., 1995. Litter decomposition, climate and litter
183 quality. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 10, 63-66.
- 184 Curiel Yuste, J., Baldocchi, D.D., Gershenson, A., Goldstein, A., Misson, L., Wong, S.,
185 2007. Microbial soil respiration and its dependency on carbon inputs, soil
186 temperature and moisture. *Global Change Biology* 13, 2018-2035.
- 187 Curiel Yuste, J., Penuelas, J., Estiarte, M., Garcia Mas, J., Mattana, S., Ogaya, R.,
188 Pujol, M., Sardans, J., 2011. Drought resistant fungi control soil organic matter
189 decomposition and its response to temperature. *Global Change Biology* 17, 1475-
190 1486.
- 191 De los Ángeles, C., Posada-Vergara, C. and Vargas, O., 2002. Banco de semillas
192 germinable de una comunidad vegetal de páramo húmedo sometido a quema y
193 pastoreo Parque Nacional Natural Chingaza, Colombia. *Ecotropicos* 15, 51-60.
- 194 Hofstede, R. “El páramo como espacio para la fijación de carbono atmosférico.” in *El*
195 *páramo como espacio de mitigación de carbono atmosférico*. Serie Páramo, N°1,
196 G. Medina and P. Mena, Eds. Quito, Ecuador: GTP/Abya-Yala, 1999, pp. 1–57.
- 197 Hartley, I.P., Heinemeyer, A., Evans, S.P., Ineson, P., 2007. The effect of soil warming
198 on bulk soil vs. rhizosphere respiration. *Global Change Biology* 13, 2654-2667.
- 199 Holmes, M. E., Chanton, J. P., Tfaily, M. M., Ogram A.C.G.B., 2014. CO₂ and CH₄
200 isotope compositions and production pathways in a tropical peatland. *Global*
201 *Biogeochemical Cycles* 29, 1-18.
- 202 Hodgkins, S.B., Tfaily, M.M., McCalley, C.K., Logan, T.A., Crill, P.M., Saleska, S.R.,
203 Rich, V.I., Chanton, J.P., Changes in peat chemistry associated with permafrost

204 thaw increase greenhouse gas production. Proceedings of the National Academy of
205 Sciences 111, 5819-5824.

206 IPCC, Climate Change 2014: Impacts, Adaptation, and Vulnerability. Part A: Global and
207 Sectoral Aspects. Contribution of Working Group II to the Fifth Assessment Report
208 of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Field, C.B., V.R. Barros, D.J.
209 Dokken, K.J. United Kingdom and New York: Cambridge University Press, 2014.

210 Keller, J. K., Bridgham, S. D., 2007. Pathways of anaerobic carbon cycling across an
211 ombrotrophic-minerotrophic peatland gradient. *Limnology and Oceanography* 52,
212 96-107.

213 Lafleur, P. M., Moore, T. R., Roulet, N. T., Froking S., 2005. Ecosystem Respiration in
214 a Cool Temperate Bog Depends on Peat Temperature But Not Water Table.
215 *Ecosystems* 8, 619-629.

216 Madriñán, S., Cortés, A. J., Richardson, J. E., 2013. Páramo is the world's fastest evolving
217 and coolest biodiversity hotspot. *Frontiers in Genetics* 4, 192

218 Moore, T.R., Dalva, M., 1997. Methane and carbon dioxide exchange potentials of peat
219 soils in aerobic and anaerobic laboratory incubations. *Soil Biology and*
220 *Biochemistry* 29, 1157-1164.

221 Morales, M., Otero, J., Van der Hammen, T., Torres, A., Cadena, C., Pedraza, C.,
222 Rodríguez, N., Franco, C., Betancourth, J.C., Olaya, E., Posada, E. y Cárdenas, L.,
223 2007. Atlas de páramos de Colombia. Instituto de Investigación de Recursos
224 Biológicos Alexander von Humboldt. Bogotá, D. C. 208 p.

225 Moyano, F. E., Vasilyeva, N., Bouckaert, L., Cook, F., Craine, J., Curiel Yuste, J., Don,
226 A., Epron, D., 2012. The moisture response of soil heterotrophic respiration:
227 interaction with soil properties. *Biogeosciences* 9, 1173-1182.

228 Podwojewski, P., Poulenard, J., Zambrana, T., Hofstede, R., 2002. Overgrazing effects
229 on vegetation cover and properties of volcanic ash soil in the páramo of Llangahua
230 and La Esperanza Tungurahua, Ecuador. *Soil Use and Management* 18, 45-55.

231 Poulenard, J. R. M., Podwojewski, P., Herbillon, A. J., 2003. Characteristics of non-
232 allophanic Andisols with hydric properties from the Ecuadorian páramos.
233 *Geoderma* 117, 267-281.

234 Treat, C. C., Natali, S. M., Ernakovich, J., Iversen, C. M., Lupascu, M., McGuire, A. D.,
235 Norby, R. J., Roy Chowdhury, T., 2015. A pan-Arctic synthesis of CH₄ and CO₂
236 production from anoxic soil incubations. *Global Change Biology* 21, 2787-2803.

237 Vile, M. A., Bridgham, S. D., Wieder, R. K., Novák, M. C., 2003. Atmospheric sulfur
238 deposition alters pathways of gaseous carbon production in peatlands. *Global*
239 *Biogeochemical Cycles* 17, 1058

240 Waddington, J. M., Rotenberg, P. A., Warren, F. J., 2001. Peat CO₂ production in a
241 natural and cutover peatland: Implications for restoration. *Biogeochemistry* 54,
242 115-130.

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SITE	N	C%		N%		S%		C/N ratio	
		Mean	SEM	Mean	SEM	Mean	SEM	Mean	SEM
CH	10	21,7	1,3	1,2	0,1	0,2	0,0	19,7	2,9
MT	10	22,7	3,1	1,3	0,2	0,2	0,0	18,4	0,8

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Table 1. Average values and standard errors of the means (SEM) for carbon (C%), nitrogen (N%), and sulfate (S%) dry weight (dw) concentrations, as well as for C/N ratios determined from the soils sampled in Chaleche (CH) and Matarredonda (MT) Páramos. No significant differences were detected between sites for any of the variables (T-test; p-value > 0,05).

257 **Figure captions**

258

259 **Figure 1.** Rates of R_H (normalized by C content) as a function of soil moisture
260 (normalized by percentage of water pore saturation) and incubation temperature (9, 22,
261 29 and 37 °C) in soils from Matarredonda (MT) (a) and Chaleche (CH) (b).

262

263 **Figure 2.** Results from the general linear model (GLM) representing the effect of soil
264 moisture (% water saturation of soil pore space) and incubation temperature over R_H from
265 soils of Matarredonda (MT) (a) and Chaleche (CH) (b).

266

267 **Figure 3.** Sensitivity of R_H to temperature (Q_{10}) as a function of soil moisture and site.
268 Error bars represent the standard error of the means.

269

270 **Figure 4.** Comparison between averaged rates of R_H obtained by incubating soils from
271 different biomes (Northern and temperate peatlands and wetlands, Mediterranean forest
272 and grassland, Alpine conifers), and results obtained in this study under aerobic (Ae) and
273 anaerobic (An) conditions. Part of the data used in this figure is taken from the literature
274 as follows: the rates of anaerobic R_H for northern peatlands were obtained from Bridgham
275 *et al.* (1998), Waddington *et al.* (2001), Moore and Dalva (1997), Hogdkins *et al.* (2014),
276 Treat *et al.* (2015), Keller and Bridgham (2007); the rates of aerobic R_H for northern
277 peatlands were obtained from Bridgham *et al.* (1998); Waddington *et al.* (2001), Moore
278 and Dalva (1997), Lafleur *et al.* (2005); the rates of aerobic R_H obtained from
279 Mediterranean broadleaf and conifer forest and grassland were obtained from Curiel
280 Yuste *et al.* (2007); the rates of anaerobic R_H for tropical peatlands were obtained from
281 Holmes *et al.* (2014); and the rates of aerobic R_H for tropical peatlands were obtained
282 from Cabaneiro *et al.* (2007). The rates of anaerobic and aerobic R_H for Páramos are those
283 measured in this study under 100% water saturation and in the range between 90-60 %
284 water saturation (no water limiting), respectively. Error bars represent the standard error
285 of the mean R_H (vertical) and mean incubation temperature (horizontal).

286